

Automated Machine Learning Approach in Material Discovery of Hole Selective Layers for
Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

In the rapidly emerging field of perovskite solar cells, rational hole selective layer development is considered a double-engine of this progress. To tap into the full potential and accelerate the commercialization path, Machine Learning (ML) is being tasked for perovskite screening and on organic semiconductors core group based on phthalocyanines, pyridine, triazatruxene, thiophenes, carbazole, and phenothiazine to yield efficient solar cells. However, sincere efforts have not led to the design of hole selective layers. Here we demonstrate how ML can be applied to the advancement of hole transport materials (HTMs) to accelerate the development. We evaluated the influence of various HTMs with various groups on the optoelectronic features and photovoltaic performance and validated it using both the random forest model and AutoML framework General Automated Machine Learning Assistant (GAMA). To this end, we utilized the GAMA to predict the suitability of hole selective layers and it returned a 0.0542 ± 0.0470 RMSE score for 15 different materials on average. We (i) established correlations between experimental and predicted results; and (ii) implemented GAMA for HTM suitability prediction. This paves the way for judicious and effective ways to overcome the bottleneck in the development of HTMs. In particular, the prediction approach on optoelectronic features and photovoltaic performance from GAMA is an effective, reliable, and fast methodology and is pioneering in the field of hole transport material screening.

1. Introduction

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have become one of the most promising photovoltaic technologies for research and development owing to their low processing cost, low amounts of materials used during fabrication, and their expeditious enhancement in the power conversion efficiency (PCE).^[1] The advancement made in the efficiency of PSCs from a mere 3.8 to 25.7% in the past decade is stunning and has fueled further scientific development.^[2] In PSCs, the perovskite layer is sandwiched between an electron transport material (ETM) and hole transporting material (HTM),^[3,4] irrespective of the device architect, and can be classified as a typical (n-i-p) and inverted (p-i-n) type structures. Here, n- and p-type represent ETM and HTM, respectively, while “i” denotes the light-harvesting layer.^[5] The subtle difference between these two PSC structures is the carrier extraction direction,^[6] in a typical (n-i-p) PSC, electrons are ejected through the transparent conductive oxide electrode while the holes are ejected through the top metal electrode. Conversely, in the p-i-n type PSCs, holes are ejected through the bottom transparent conductive oxide electrode while electrons are extracted through the top metal electrode.^[6] Perovskites do show ambipolar behavior, however, the holes are minority carriers and for real-world device purposes, the use of HTM is indispensable.

Regardless of the type of PSCs, HTM plays an essential role in facilitating photogenerated hole extraction and transport, lowering the energy barrier between the perovskite and electrode, and suppressing interface charge recombination, which are essential to attain high PCE.^[7-9] Moreover, the use of HTM can also ensure absorber protection from deleterious environmental factors such as moisture and metal diffusion from ambient and electrode, and boost stability. PSCs using HTMs have anticipated features such as high stability and chemical compatibility that can effectively improve longevity.^[10] Until now, 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) is one of the most widely used organic semiconductors as HTM in high-performance PSCs fabrication. However, Spiro-OMeTAD involves tedious, and high-cost synthetic routes that show UV instability and low electrical features. Sincere efforts are being laid to the search and development of cost-effective and efficient alternatives to Spiro-OMeTAD.^[8-10] An organic core composed of phthalocyanines, pyridine, triazatruxene, thiophenes, carbazole, and phenothiazine-based compounds has gained considerable attention as HTMs due to their

cost-effective synthesis steps and purification processes, and durability under thermal and light conditions.^[3,4,7,11]

Machine learning (ML) models have been broadly exploited in several application areas of science and engineering including the screening of the material used for PSCs, and have gained considerable attention recently to exploit their full potential and accelerate the commercialization path. ML is a class of artificial intelligence (AI), that allows computers to learn how to implement a specific task.^[2] Screening compound datasets from experiments together with the ML approach can drastically decrease research time, which is paramount to discovering high-performance materials.¹² ML techniques have been utilized to predict electro-optical properties, band gap, durability, and structural and electronic features of hybrid perovskites to decipher the material efficacy and overcome the materials design problems.^[13–15] The estimation from ML can specify an apparent direction for high-performance material discovery and advanced experimental efficiency, rather than trial and error.^[15] Vakharia *et al.* evaluated a data set consisting of 240 perovskites to predict the bandgap calculated from a pool of diverse cations and associated structures using two machine learning models: ElasticNet and Isotonic Regression. While the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.09 eV was attained for Cesium (Cs)-based perovskites from ElasticNet and ten-fold cross-validation results, the highest MAE of 0.34 eV was attained for methylammonium (MA)-based perovskites with Isotonic Regression.^[13] The influence of potassium iodide (KI) doping on the performance of PSCs was investigated and the optimal doping KI concentration was attained as 3% using the ML method, leading to the PCE of 20.91% with a high FF of 80% using 3% KI-doped MAPbI₃.^[2] The ML approach has been also extended to optimize the perovskite capping layer to assist capping-layer design rules that can solve perovskite degradation.^[16] Liu *et al.* evaluated 49 ML approaches utilizing 814 real experimental data sets from published articles and 7 ML algorithms (Bandgap_{XGBoost}, CBM_{XGBoost}, VBM_{XGBoost}, PCE_{RF}, V_{ocRF} , J_{scRF} , and FF_{RF}) to predict the performance of PSCs. Note here, that CBM represents conduction band minimum, while VBM, is referred to as valence band maximum. The experimental and prediction results of PCE show relatively high correlation and low RMSE (*root mean square error*), with an r-value of 0.86, and RMSE of 1.58.^[17] Yan *et al.* demonstrated a strategy and applicability to boost unknown perovskite for solar cell application by combining approaches of ML and light management.^[18]

Small molecules-based HTMs are considered potential alternatives for Spiro-OMeTAD and are extensively developed through a molecular engineering approach, are cost-effective, with an opportunity to tune the electro-optical properties and energy level. In this work, we computed a series of HTMs having metal phthalocyanines (MPcs, M = Zn or Cu), pyridine, and substituted phenothiazine core. The molecular structures of HTMs investigated are shown (**Figure 1**). The investigated HTMs and their data set is collected for training and testing ML models. For each material group (Table 1), one PSC has been kept hidden and used as test data while the rest of the PSCs from the same material group were used for training to contribute to a material discovery. Stimulated by experimental results on the design of HTMs into PSCs, as well as on utilizing ML models to evaluate the optical features and PSC performance, we purpose an ML approach to predict the influence of HTMs with different substitution groups on the optical band gap and solar cell performance. Our work provides detailed insight into the impact of HTMs with varied core and substitution groups on optical band gap and solar cell performance, to allow the renaissance of HTMs and identify a promising candidate.

2. Experimental

2.1 Device fabrication

The device fabrication process is adopted according to our previous reports, describing the device fabrication steps and the source of the chemical used. The chemicals and reagents used are commercially available and used without further purification, except for the hole transport materials. For ease of understanding and comparison, purposes, the perovskite layer was kept uniform and can be formulated as $(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.97}(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.03}$, in all the predictions.^[3,4] The specific HTM (**Figure 1**) was synthesized and used as described ^[3,4,7,11], from a solution of chlorobenzene with common additives (LiTFSI and *t*-BP with a mole ratio of 0.5 and 3.3, respectively), while the standard Spiro-OMeTAD was prepared by dissolving 72.3 mg/mL in chlorobenzene with 17.5 μL LiTFSI solution (520 mg/mL in acetonitrile) and 28.8 μL *t*-BP. The molar concentration of specific HTMs was according to our earlier reports.^[4,11] Similarly, the device characterization has been adopted as presented previously. One of the main merits of this work is that the device fabrication and characterization steps were similar for all the data and data was generated from a single lab using a similar process, lab condition, and characterization techniques.

Figure 1. Chemical structures of various hole transport materials.

2.2 Prediction Models

With an increase in the number of experiments and data collection, it becomes challenging to analyze and discover patterns in chemical processes. In this context, ML algorithms become useful for monitoring data in chemical processes, to uncover hidden patterns without giving precise instructions to machines so that they can develop representative models from the data. For processing different data sets, a variety of ML algorithms may be applied. Random Forests (RF) are among these algorithms and are often preferred in ML studies due to their flexibility and high performance.^[19] It is an ensemble approach that employs numerous individual tree structures and can be used for both classification and regression tasks. When the task is learned, the random forest analyzes each tree and makes decisions based on a majority vote. On the other hand,

when the task is regression, the mean of the output values from each tree is returned. To utilize the full potential of Random Forest, similar to any other algorithm, manual engineering for data preprocessing and hyperparameter optimization is required.

Table 1. Classification of HTLs in Material Groups

Material Group 1	Material Group 2	Material Group 3	Material Group 4	Material Group 5
2PyPTPDA _n	2,6PyDANCBZ	PTADANCBZ	ZnPcTB4	CuPcTB4
3PyPTPDA _n	3,5PyDANCBZ	PTODANCBZ	ZnPcAE	CuPcAE
4PyPTPDA _n			ZnPcTDZ	CuPcTDZ
			ZnPcTTPA	CuPcTTPA
Number of Observations				
74 per PSC	52 per PSC	102 per PSC	99 per PSC	92 per PSC
Number of Descriptors (Wavelength, Absorbance, Open Circuit Potential, and Current Density)				
6 Features, 1 Target	4 Features, 1 Target	4 Features, 1 Target	8 Features, 1 Target	8 Features, 1 Target

A new evolving area of ML is known as automated machine learning (AutoML), which considers the optimal selection and configuration of data preprocessing, learning algorithm, and its hyperparameters at once to find the best performing pipeline (**Figure 2**) on a given dataset within a provided computation budget.²⁰ Therefore, AutoML frameworks mitigate overwhelming manual engineering processes while promising robust results. To solve Combined Algorithm Selection and Hyperparameter Optimization (CASH) problem, an open source AutoML framework General Automated Machine Learning Assistant (GAMA) is employed in this study. GAMA explores various kinds of data preprocessing techniques (e.g. dimension reduction, scaling, and normalization), traditional ML algorithms, and their hyperparameters by evolutionary search.^[21] We executed GAMA to let it create the best pipeline and make predictions. To compare the results we selected the Random Forest with default hyperparameters as a baseline model. To induce a fair comparison, GAMA and Random Forest was run with five-fold cross-validation and RMSE scores are presented.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of AutoML

3. Results and Discussions

The predicted materials are classified according to their core and substituents group (Table 1) and their molecular structure is presented in Figure 1, each group is considered separately during the construction of the ML models as their physicochemical and electrochemical properties vary with the core group present. In each material group, one PSC was kept hidden and used as test data. The remaining PSCs in the same material group were trained to contribute to a material discovery.^[22] For example, to create a realistic scenario, we assumed that there is no information available for 4PyPTPDAn yet we have an access to all information from the rest of the material group: wavelength and its respective absorbance values for both 2PyPTPDAn and 3PyPTPDAn; and also open circuit potential (V_{oc}) and its corresponding short circuit current density (J_{sc}) values for both 2PyPTPDAn and 3PyPTPDAn. We computed a machine learning approach for predicting the optical band gap and PSCs performance of HTMs with various substitution groups. Findings and outcomes are presented in the following subsections.

3.1. Optical Properties prediction

In the first section, the aim is to obtain a prominent ML model that predicts optical bandgap (E_g) based on wavelength (nm) and absorbance values (supporting info, Figure S1-S15). Thus the wavelength (nm) values of unhidden PSCs were provided to train ML algorithms and to predict corresponding absorbance (a.u.) values. For example, we hide data of the 2PyPTPDAn and stored it as a test set. The rest of the PSCs from the same material group, namely 3PyPTPDAn and 4PyPTPDAn, were used in model training. In other words, we expected models to be able to discover 2PyPTPDAn without visualizing

any data about it. Therefore, we employed GAMA to create optimal machine learning models for predicting absorbance (a.u.) values of each hidden PSC, and to validate the success of our approach, Random Forest was selected as a baseline. The average RMSE score of train and test sets for Random Forest is 0.0609 and 0.0786 respectively while they were 0.0099 and 0.0373 for the GAMA framework. An average relative improvement of 68% is observed for both train and test performances while 50% relative improvement is achieved on the standard deviation of the performance. This suggests that GAMA is much more stable and adaptive than Random Forest, and demonstrates the suitability of these algorithms. RMSE scores of absorbance predictions for each material are detailed in Supporting Info, Table S2. Further, optical bandgap (E_g) values derived from the predictions were compared with the real optical bandgap (E_g) values and GAMA outperformed RF in 12 cases out of 15 (**Table 2**). To note here, it is better in material groups 3, 4, and 5. As an example, we compared real absorbance values with predicted absorbance values for ZnPcTB4 (Figure 3).

Table 2. Optical bandgap (E_g) values derived from experiments, GAMA, and RF for different HTLs.

HTML	E_g (eV)	GAMA E_g (eV)	RF E_g (eV)
2PyPTPDAn	3.10	3.09	3.13
3PyPTPDAn	2.85	2.88	2.87
4PyPTPDAn	2.98	3.02	3.03
2,6PyDAnCBZ	2.85	2.77	2.78
3,5PyDAnCBZ	2.84	2.79	2.78
PTADAnCBZ	3.00	2.95	2.92
PTODAnCBZ	2.86	2.81	2.79
ZnPcTB4	1.77	1.73	1.72
ZnPcAE	1.78	1.73	1.72
ZnPcTDZ	1.64	1.58	1.57
ZnPcTTPA	1.73	1.72	1.64
CuPcTB4	1.76	1.75	1.74
CuPcAE	1.76	1.76	1.73
CuPcTDZ	1.61	1.62	1.62
CuPcTTPA	1.72	1.72	1.68

3.2. Photovoltaic Properties prediction

In the second section, open circuit potential (V_{oc}) and short circuit current density (J_{sc}) are used to find another prominent ML model that ultimately predicts the photovoltaic parameter PCE. Similar to the first section, V_{oc} values of unhidden PSCs were provided to train machine learning algorithms and predict the corresponding J_{sc} (mA/cm^2) values.

Figure 3. Comparison of true and predicted absorbance values for ZnPcTB4.

In this experiment, the average RMSE scores of train and test sets for RF are found to be 0.1789 and 0.2391 respectively while they were 0.0713 and 0.0711 for the GAMA framework. A relative improvement of 65% was observed for both train and test performances while 63.5% relative improvement was achieved on the standard deviation of the performance. That shows again that GAMA is much more stable and adaptive than RF while working on PV parameters evaluation as well. The RMSE scores of J_{sc} (mA/cm^2) predictions for each material are presented (Supporting info Table S2). Further, the PCE values are calculated from the predictions and compared with the experimental PCE values. We noted that GAMA outperformed RF in 10 out of 15 cases as in **Table 3**. We noted it specifically better for material groups 2, 4, and 5. As an example, real J values compared with predicted J values (**Figure 4**) for ZnPcAE and the P-V graph of PSCs are presented (Figure 5 and 6).

Table 3. Photovoltaic PCE (%) values derived from the experiments, GAMA, and RF for different HTLs

HTM	Measured PCE (%)	Predicted PCE (%) with GAMA	Predicted PCE (%) with RF
2PyPTPDAn	16.05	15.99	16.07
3PyPTPDAn	17.94	17.87	17.90
4PyPTPDAn	0.40	0.40	0.40
2,6PyDAnCBZ	17.78	17.53	17.19
3,5PyDAnCBZ	16.07	15.48	15.47
PTADAnCBZ	17.01	16.95	16.91
PTODAnCBZ	17.72	17.72	17.72
ZnPcTB4	10.55	10.51	10.68
ZnPcAE	14.25	14.14	14.20
ZnPcTDZ	13.30	13.31	13.39
ZnPcTTPA	9.97	9.95	10.09
CuPcTB4	14.88	14.91	14.80
CuPcAE	10.07	10.16	10.17
CuPcTDZ	10.34	10.31	10.29
CuPcTTPA	14.40	14.43	14.34

Figure 4. Comparison of true and predicted J values for ZnPcAE.

Figure 5. Machine learning simulation and measured P-V graph of PSCs based on a) 2PyPTPDAn, b) 3 PyPTPDAn, c) 4PyPTPDAn, d) 2,6PyDANCbZ, e) 3,5PyDANCbZ f) PTADAnCBZ, and g) PTODAnCBZ.

AutoML is an effective tool for various domains and expertise. It was able to excel in a well-known robust RF model even with a provided 180 seconds computation and prediction budget. It is found that the model generated by GAMA performs much more consistently and responsive than RF. We argue that AutoML would be much more beneficial while working with more complex tasks and datasets. It will pave the way for the democratization of machine learning by enabling many fields to use artificial intelligence in their applications.

Figure 6: Machine learning simulation and measured P-V graph of PSCs based on a) ZnPcTB4, b) ZnPcAE, c) ZnPcTDZ, d) ZnPcTTPA e) CuPcTB4 f) CuPcAE g) CuPcTDZ h) CuPcTTPA.

4. Conclusions

To conclude, we have established a design prediction based on the core and substituents group of organic semiconductors that provides information about materials' intrinsic properties and suitability for HTMs and trained experimental data sets for various ML models based to conceal hidden patterns. The scarcity of reports dealing with ML-based approaches delayed the rapid development and unified hole selective layer core group as hole transport materials design and development. The established correlation and validation of experimental methodologies will boost the research and development efforts in hole selective materials for the thin film PV community and will act as a guiding path for new molecular design. Our displayed results overcome the complexity behind the design principle of HTM and make the synthetic task easy, to identify the right materials and their optimization. Our adopted algorithm that generates machine learning models with AutoML framework GAMA will substantially accelerate the

discovery of innovative organic semiconductors to be used as hole selective layers in perovskite solar cells to boost its candidacy for thin-film PV.

Keywords

AutoML, Hole selective layers, Machine Learning, Perovskite solar cells, Photovoltaic properties

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the discussions and data collection of this work and the final version is prepared with all the authors. SA directed the research.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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